

PERCEPTION OF MALAYSIAN WORKING ADULTS ON TAX EXEMPTION FOR PURCHASING INSURANCE FOR PARENTS WITH PRE-EXISTING ILLNESS

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ABSTRACT

Some things in life are not worth risking, for instance our health and financial wellbeing. However, nearly half of the Malaysian population relies solely on government-supplied healthcare coverage and out-of-pocket expenses. They have no additional personal health insurance for their personal healthcare needs. The rise in the cost of healthcare has had an impact on access to care, especially for those with pre-existing conditions. This study aims to determine the acceptance and overall perception of working adults towards a tax exemption incentive for purchasing insurance that covers pre-existing medical illness expenses for their elderly parents. The findings would benefit senior citizens with pre-existing illnesses and catalyse insurance companies to develop health coverage for vulnerable populations. Additionally, the suggestions or recommendations may be useful for the government in putting forward policies that are advantageous for the healthcare system in Malaysia. This study utilises a cross-sectional design with descriptive statistic research methods, specifically survey instrumentation in a questionnaire form to collect data using a convenience sampling method. The survey form was given out and collected online through e-mail and Qualtrics, an online survey tool. Overall, 345 working adults in Malaysia participated in this study. The findings of this study show that working adults in Malaysia are likely to purchase health coverage for parents, have a positive attitude towards tax exemption for purchasing health coverage for parents and have a good intention to support tax incentives in purchasing health insurance for parents.

Keywords: healthcare, insurance, parents, pre-existing illness, tax exemption, working adults

INTRODUCTION

There is no tax exemption for purchasing insurance for parents with pre-existing illnesses in Malaysia. This could benefit many if such an incentive existed to accommodate the growing ageing population and increasing complex and diverse health needs. According to (Chen & Jin, 2012), health insurance policies are in demand of prioritising safety and family protection.

The opportunity for the health insurance market to bloom in Malaysia is very likely to happen as a smaller proportion of Malaysians are covered under Malaysian Health Insurance (MHI) policies. The financial burden on individuals is lessened with the increased health system performance due to health insurance.

Generally, an individual with a pre-existing condition is considered a high risk as their condition may result in the individual needing high-cost health care services. For this same reason, individuals who are aware of their existing health conditions are more likely to have a health insurance plan.

In Malaysia, though the economy is progressing quickly, the healthcare system faces some major problems. The (*Institute for Public Health - NHMS, 2019*) reported that approximately 81% of Malaysians use their income to pay for healthcare services, 36% use their savings, and 11% borrow from their family and friends, other than household members, to pay for healthcare services. The escalating healthcare expenditure cost impacts the national government and certain vulnerable populations. Among them is the senior citizen population, which is predicted to reach 10% of the general population by 2025. The health care cost in Malaysia for this vulnerable population has also been on the hike in recent years at an average of about 15% annually. A major reason for this hike is the increased prevalence of non-communicable diseases among the ageing population. This scenario is further escalated by Malaysia's low number of insured senior citizens. Without proper insurance coverage, the massive cost of disease management among the ageing population creates a cost burden for the country.

Insurance is not a foreign concept and is known to be one of the oldest known financial products. Insurance involves developing the modern business against risks, especially property, death, automobile accidents, and health or medical treatment. The insurance industry helps to reduce risks, spreads risks from the individual to the broader community, and offers a significant source of long-term funding for both the public and private sectors. However, there is still a majority that will not willingly purchase it. This may be because insurance is a complicated product or concept for some. Besides that, Malaysia, being an Asian country with diverse cultures, is considered taboo for some to speak about adverse circumstances such as death, disability, or ill health. However, given that life is full of uncertainties, insurance helps protect and ease the damage suffered by consumers and households in the event of such unfortunate events happening (Loke & Goh, 2013).

Currently, tax relief in Malaysia is given to people with disabilities and their caregivers as included in the Income Tax Act 1967. This exemption is a deduction from the taxpayer's total income in ascertaining his/her chargeable income, as for caregivers. The tax relief is contained in Section 46(1)(c) of the Act, entitles "Medical Expenses for Parents", which was initially intended only to provide support for medical expenses incurred in respect of a parent but in 2011 was later revised to include special needs of the parent and caregiver expenses incurred by the taxpayer himself/herself, his/her spouse or child. Other eligibility requirements specify that the parents should be provided in Malaysia, and the medical practitioner should be registered with the Malaysian

Medical Council. Nonetheless, the government has made commendable efforts to recognise that some individuals have special needs and require the services of a caregiver. The Malaysian government has been accustomed to the taxation system as a measure to provide financial aid to people with disabilities and special needs as well as their caregivers for decades now. The government has integrated several tax reliefs into its tax legislation to provide aid and lessen the burden on disabled persons (Nair & Devi, 2015).

Families caring for disabled or chronically ill members are increasingly made to support and bear the responsibility even with medical care offered by a country, and it has made repeated calls for interventions by the government in terms of fiscal policies and mechanisms to support such families (Montgomery et al., 1985). Besides physical health, psychological health problems are also rampant among the elderly in Malaysia (Mohd Sidik et al., 2003).

A study (Glied & Jackson, 2017) found that if pre-existing conditions were excluded from coverage in the United States of America, there would be a higher out-of-pocket expense for nearly all people with those conditions. The average out-of-pocket expenses would triple for people with cancer or diabetes while the cost of treatment for arthritis, asthma, and hypertension would increase from 27 percent to 39 percent. Some may see even more significant increases; for example, 10 percent of patients with diabetes would expect to pay more than \$9,200 in out-of-pocket costs annually. Those with pre-existing conditions would, therefore, spend more on conditions that are not excluded, as out-of-pocket costs on their pre-existing conditions would no longer count against the deductible and out-of-pocket limit. Different countries have various methods of arranging finances regarding taxes, private payments, and social insurance. Malaysia currently still does not have a national social health insurance scheme.

Consumer behaviour is when an individual decides what, where, how, and how to buy goods and services. Consumer behaviour studies how people, groups, and organisations select, purchase, and use products, services, ideas, or experiences to fulfil their needs and desires. This enables marketers to analyse, anticipate, and understand customer behaviour in the marketplace. It is concerned with what consumers purchase and why, when, and how much they purchase it (Kumar & Namavaram, 2016).

(Brown & Swartz, 1989) defined perception as the belief of the consumer in the received or experienced service. The horror stories of insurance fraud may cloud consumers' perceptions when purchasing insurance. Therefore, individuals prefer to purchase health insurance from friends, colleagues, or relatives based on trust towards the insurer company or from positive word of mouth (Blodgett et al., 1997). Insurance fraud cases are a serious crime and must be tackled. There are a lot of complaints and dissatisfaction from consumers on the claiming process from insurance providers or just the insurance providers themselves.

Customers tend to be specific about how trustworthy they can be to an insurance provider. They would want an insurance provider that would be reliable and readily available to assist them should any problems regarding their claims and insurance policy arise (Duodu & Amankwah, 2012). As the person is affected by how the majority thinks or acts, it is referred to as majority influence. A person is said to comply if they choose a course of action favoured or considered socially acceptable by the majority. However, the fact that an individual conforms with the majority does not automatically imply that they have changed their private outlook or beliefs. Therefore, most of the majority influence is characterised by public compliance rather than private acceptance.

Social influence has been considered one of the significant factors affecting an individual's demand for purchasing insurance. The change in behaviour that a single person causes in another, either intentionally or unintentionally, as a result of the way the changed person perceives things is known as social influence. These include the influences of one's family, the effect of friends and peers, the insurance company, etc. Individuals may learn more about health insurance from their family, friends, and the people around them. It was suggested that there is a positive relationship between social impact and the demand for purchasing health insurance (Ulbinaitė et al., 2013). This may be when an individual sees their family, friends, and neighbours involved in an imprudent uninsured tragedy; it creates fear in themselves, thus changing their perception of health insurance and believing that being covered by insurance is necessary and will end up purchasing it.

Individuals have greater health insurance awareness and knowledge through observational learning and word-of-mouth communication (Sun et al., 2019). However, (Ackah & Owusu, 2012) found that while many people know the word insurance from their family and friends, they have found that they seem not to want to purchase insurance to protect themselves from potential unpredicted misfortunes in the future. (Cai et al., 2015) reported that households are more likely not to purchase insurance if they have weaker related friends and friends who do not have strong knowledge of insurance purchases.

A famous quote goes, "Money makes the world go round". This depicts how money is an essential element of society. Nowadays, there is no doubt that one's salary affects their lifestyle choices and purchase of insurance. The employee's salary often influences insurance purchases. There are typically two types of employees, one being blue-collar and the other being white-collar. (Burnett & Palmer, 1984) stated how white-collar workers usually have a higher wage than blue-collar workers. Thus, they will have more intention to purchase. Typically, white-collar workers have a more stable income as they have a more stable job, and blue-collar workers are usually paid hourly; thus, their future income is less specific. Ultimately, the demand for purchasing insurance is significantly influenced by how wealthy the wage earners are (Pliska & Ye, 2007). Research (Abdel-Ghany & Wang, 2001) showed that about 50% of families with a self-employed person are more likely to purchase health insurance coverage, compared to 66% of families with a person employed in a government position or corporate position, were more likely to be covered by some insurance policy.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The Malaysian healthcare system comprises tax-funded and government-run universal services and a fast-growing private sector. The Ministry of Health administers public sector health services centrally and is organised under a civil service structure. The Ministry of Health plans and regulates most public sector health services but exerts little regulatory power over the private sector (World Health Organization, 2013).

While excluding individuals with pre-existing conditions entirely and extending coverage for the rest of the individual or family's health exclusive of the condition may be the simplest and most savvy approach, insurers understand that this is not always acceptable or practical. Malaysia has three primary methods and options for arranging coverage for anyone with a pre-existing health condition: Moratorium for Coverage, Medical History Disregarded, and Premium Loading. The insurer usually reviews the possibility of inclusion for pre-existing conditions on a case-to-case basis. A consumer needs to note that different insurance companies have different regulations and

options for pre-existing condition coverage and influence the cost, type of condition involved and other variables such as the individual's age.

The National Health and Morbidity Survey (NHMS) showed a steady increase in healthcare spending from total household monthly expenditure from 4.6% in 2015 to 5.1% in 2019. It was found that there was a higher percentage of Malaysians who utilised in-patient government healthcare services (76%) compared to private facilities (24%). According to the NHMS, in 2019, more Malaysians sought outpatient care in government facilities (64.6%) compared to 36.3% in private facilities, a much higher number compared to previous years (*Institute for Public Health - NHMS, 2019*). Though it has not been made clear why people would opt for government facilities for healthcare, if healthcare costs are not contained, the increase in medical and health premiums will be inevitable. Once medical insurance becomes unaffordable, it would cause more patients to seek treatment in government hospitals and facilities, further aggravating the already burdened health system.

The (*World Health Report, n.d.*) defines an expenditure as 'catastrophic' if a household's health care costs exceed 40% of income remaining after subsistence needs are met. Out-of-pocket payments (OOP) are the principal means of financing health care throughout Asia. In middle-income Asian countries, including Malaysia, the catastrophic impact of health costs on the poor pushing households into poverty is better constrained than in poor countries, and better-off households spend more on health care than the poor (van Doorslaer et al., 2006). Individuals with medical coverage provided through government, employers or private insurance funds could better use private health care. They had higher mean household expenditure on health than those not covered. If an individual suffers from any medical condition or disease before taking a health insurance policy, such a condition is termed a pre-existing medical disease or condition. This may include any health issue, from severe conditions like cancer or diabetes to slightly less serious conditions like high blood pressure, asthma, or acne. Health insurance companies are seldom willing to provide coverage to individuals who are suffering from any pre-existing medical condition. This is because such individuals would be in greater need of medical assistance, posing a higher financial risk to the insurance company. For this reason, health insurance providers will be hesitant to provide a policy to individuals who are suffering from a pre-existing condition. It is not easy for such individuals to find adequate insurance coverage. Often, their insurance policies could be cancelled, the insurer may refuse to cover the medical bills, or, at worst, insurers may refuse to provide a health insurance policy altogether.

A study has been conducted regarding this issue among working adults in Malaysia. Therefore, it is assumed that this study will help partially fill the literature gap and provide recent evidence on working adults' perception of tax exemption for purchasing parent's insurance covering pre-existing medical illness.

This research aims to recognise the perception of Malaysian working adults on tax exemption for purchasing parent's insurance covering pre-existing medical illnesses. It is also to explore and/or offer various and better healthcare services for consumers and help the economy in terms of healthcare so it becomes accessible and affordable for everyone. This research may help insurance companies in Malaysia to develop health coverage for vulnerable populations. Additionally, the suggestions or recommendations may be helpful for the government in putting forward policies that are advantageous for the healthcare system in Malaysia.

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the attitudes and perception of working adults towards a tax exemption incentive for parents' health coverage purchase.
- To examine the intention to support working adults on tax exemptions for parents' health coverage purchases.

METHODOLOGY

SAMPLING METHOD

For certain studies, the population might be small enough to justify all of them being included in the sample. That, unfortunately, might not be the case for studies that entail a large population that cannot all be studied. Consequently, a sample in this research is a smaller group drawn through elements of inclusion criteria set by the researchers. With regard to the large number of working adults in Malaysia, convenience sampling was done for all working adults who are a part of the Malaysian Trades Union Congress (MTUC) and the Congress of Union of Employees in the Public and Civil Services Malaysia (CUEPACS). Approval letter or letter of agreement on research collaboration for this study was obtained from MTUC and CUEPACS before the start of the study, and copies of such agreement were submitted to PU-IRB.

POPULATION SELECTION

Malaysian working adults who are paying annual taxes using the BE form. We include all respondents with income above RM36,000 per year. There is no specific inclusion clause for parents with illness or insurance. This clause is irrelevant to this study as it only requires the opinions of all working adults.

In Malaysia, the total population of working adults from the CUEPACS and MTUC databases is 1,200,000 and 500,000, respectively. Using the Raosoft Survey Tools sample size calculator, the sample is estimated to be 385.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

The online study questionnaire web link was distributed to email addresses of members of the Congress of the Union of Employees of Public and Civil Services (CUEPACS) Malaysia and the Malaysian Trade Union Congress (MTUC). Inferred consent was obtained by asking the respondents to complete a tick box on the questionnaire. The sample size was determined based on an acceptable level of significance ($p \leq 0.05$) and the power of the study. A minimum of 345 working adults were recruited for this study in Malaysia.

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

Data analysis focuses on applying statistical or logical techniques to describe and evaluate data. This study and its data were analysed using SPSS, a statistical software. SPSS, also known as Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, is a widely used comprehensive statistical analysis application for data analysis. It can perform highly complex data manipulation and analysis in large amounts with simple instructions.

The data obtained was analysed to identify both descriptive and causal relationships. Standard normality, validity and reliability assessment, correlation and regression analysis were conducted to establish causal relationships.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study and protocols used in the study were approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Perdana University (PU-IRB), Malaysia, and consent was information about the research and their participation in the study was provided in the consent form. Obtaining consent involves informing the subject about his or her rights, the purpose of the study, procedures to be undertaken, potential risks and benefits of participation, expected duration of the study, the extent of confidentiality of personal identification and demographic data so that the participation of subjects in the study is entirely voluntary. The participants were also informed about any new information that might affect their decision to continue participating. Participation by the working adults was voluntary, and the participants were informed that the information shared would be kept strictly confidential and that they could withdraw from the study at any time.

RESULTS

Table 1. The demographic profiles of the respondents.

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	DESCRIPTION	FREQUENCY (%)
Age	21-30	127 (36.8)
	31-40	76 (22.0)
	41-50	58 (16.8)
	51-60	84 (24.3)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Gender	Male	166 (48.1)
	Female	179 (51.9)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Ethnicity	Malay	207 (60.0)
	Indian	85 (24.6)
	Chinese	42 (12.2)
	Others	11 (3.2)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Marital Status	Single	127 (36.8)
	Married	202(58.6)
	Widowed	11 (3.2)
	Divorced	5 (1.4)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Number of Children	None	144 (41.7)
	1-3	144 (41.7)
	4-5	45 (13.0)
	6 and above	12(3.5)
	Total	345 (100.0)

Education Level	Primary	5 (1.4)
	Secondary	48 (13.9)
	Higher Education	292 (84.6)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Occupation	Lecturer/Teacher	57 (16.5)
	Unskilled Labour	14 (4.1)
	Business Owner	53 (15.4)
	Civil Servant	38 (11.0)
	NGO Worker	12 (3.5)
	Others	171 (49.6)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Average Monthly Income	RM3,000 – RM 3,999	139 (40.3)
	RM 4,000 – RM 4,999	64 (18.6)
	RM 5,000 – RM 5,999	39 (11.3)
	RM 6,000 and above	103 (29.9)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Do you have any health problems?	Yes	65 (18.8)
	No	280 (81.2)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Are you taking care of your parents/parents-in-law?	Father	20 (5.8)
	Mother	61 (17.7)
	Both	138 (40.0)
	None	126 (36.5)
	Total	345 (100.0)
Do your parents/parents-in-law have any pre-existing illnesses?	Yes	206 (59.7)
	No	139 (40.3)
	Total	345 (100.0)
What are their average monthly medical expenses?	RM 500 and below	162 (57.0)
	RM 500 – RM 1,000	71 (20.9)
	RM 1,000 and above	42 (12.2)
	Not applicable	69 (20.0)
	Total	345 (100.0)

It was gathered that most of the respondents were aged 21-30 years old, and a little over half were female. Besides that, most of the respondents were of Malay race, and most were married. Having no children and 1 to 3 children were equally the most common responses, and many respondents completed their higher education. The highest percentage of occupations was answered as others, and the majority had an average monthly income of RM3,000 to RM3,999. 'No' was the most common response to if the respondents had any health problems. Furthermore, when asked if they are taking care of either their parents and/or parents-in-law, the majority answered both, and more than half responded yes when asked if their parents and/or parents-in-law had any pre-existing illness. Lastly, most respondents say their parents' average monthly medical expenses were RM500 and below.

Table 2, The attitude towards tax exemption for purchasing health coverage for parents (N = 345).

ATTITUDE TOWARDS TAX EXEMPTION FOR PURCHASING HEALTH COVERAGE FOR PARENTS	FREQUENCY (%)				
	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
I think it is good to have a health insurance policy.	229 (66.4)	85 (24.6)	25 (7.2)	1 (0.3)	5 (1.4)
In general, I am satisfied with the existing Malaysian tax system.	40 (11.6)	117 (33.9)	141 (40.9)	36 (10.4)	11 (3.2)
Do you feel that the taxes implied in Malaysia are complicated to understand?	34 (9.9)	109 (31.6)	123 (35.7)	64 (18.6)	15 (4.3)
I am aware of companies offering health insurance with benefits included.	86 (24.9)	163 (47.2)	73 (21.2)	17 (4.9)	6 (1.7)
The tax incentive available for health insurance premiums is an important factor for me to take health insurance for my parents.	86 (24.9)	146 (42.3)	94 (27.2)	14 (4.1)	5 (1.4)
The experience of tax exemption settlement influences my decision to renew my parents' policies with the service provider.	74 (21.4)	142 (41.2)	101 (29.3)	10 (5.8)	8 (2.3)
Irrespective of whether I have tax exemptions or not, I will continue to renew my health insurance policy.	108 (31.3)	136 (39.4)	83 (24.1)	15 (4.3)	3 (0.9)
Promotional offers influence my decision to purchase health insurance policy for my parents.	71 (20.6)	147 (42.6)	92 (26.7)	23 (6.7)	12 (3.5)
Rising social awareness about health care has positive influence on purchasing decision of health insurance for parents.	108 (31.3)	156 (45.2)	65 (18.8)	12 (3.5)	4 (1.2)

Government schemes for health insurance for other social sectors will motivate me to purchase a health insurance policy for myself and parents.	94 (27.2)	148 (42.9)	87 (25.2)	14 (4.1)	2 (0.6)
The settlement of tax exemptions by Malaysian government in purchasing health insurance will be satisfactory.	70 (20.3)	162 (47.0)	92 (26.7)	20 (5.8)	1 (0.3)
I find it difficult to meet unexpected medical expenditures for my parents without benefits provided when purchasing health insurance.	63 (18.3)	142 (41.2)	103 (29.9)	27 (7.8)	10 (2.9)

The highest response for the statement 'I think it is good to have a health insurance policy' was strongly agree, making up with more than half of the respondents. The majority were neutral when asked if they were satisfied with the existing Malaysian tax system, followed by the same majority response of neutral when asked if they feel that the taxes implied in Malaysia are complicated to understand. Majority responses were somewhat agree to all other following questions in this section such as 'I am aware of companies offering health insurance with benefits included', 'the tax incentive available for health insurance premium is an important factor for me to take health insurance for my parents', 'the experience of tax exemption settlement influences my decision to renew my parents' policies with the service provider', 'irrespective of whether I have tax exemptions or not, I will continue to renew my health insurance policy', 'promotional offers influence my decision to purchase health insurance policy for my parents', 'rising social awareness about health care has positive influence on purchasing decision of health insurance for parents', 'government schemes for health insurance for other social sectors will motivate me to purchase a health insurance policy for myself and parents', 'the settlement of tax exemptions by Malaysian government in purchasing health insurance will be satisfactory', and lastly 'I find it difficult to meet unexpected medical expenditures for my parents without benefits provided when purchasing health insurance'.

Table 3. The intention to support tax incentive in purchasing health insurance for parents (N = 345).

INTENTION TO SUPPORT TAX INCENTIVE IN PURCHASING HEALTH INSURANCE FOR PARENTS	FREQUENCY (%)				
	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
I support the tax relief incentive for purchase of health coverage for parents.	180 (52.2)	111 (32.2)	46 (13.3)	4 (1.2)	4 (1.2)
I believe this tax incentive will be an important encouragement for me to buy health coverage for my parents.	152 (44.1)	130 (37.7)	47 (13.6)	11 (3.2)	5 (1.4)
I will encourage my friends and family to support the tax incentive for parents' health coverage.	139 (40.3)	127 (36.8)	68 (19.7)	7 (2.0)	4 (1.2)

Overall, the majority strongly agreed to statements 'I support the tax relief incentive for purchase of health coverage for parents', 'I believe this tax incentive will be an important encouragement for me to buy health coverage for my parents' and 'I will encourage my friends and family to support the tax incentive for parents' health coverage' respectively.

The analysis continues to test the study's hypothesis. The results are presented in Table 4, Table 4a and Table 4b, respectively.

Table 4. The hypothesis testing for each section and its conclusion.

HYPOTHESIS STATEMENT	P-VALUE	RESULT
Working adults have a more positive attitude and perception towards a tax exemption for purchasing parent's insurance covering pre-existing illness.	0.000	Accepted
There is an intention of working adults to support on tax exemptions for parent's health coverage purchase.	0.000	Accepted

The p-value (0.000) of attitude towards tax exemption and p-value (0.010) for intention to support tax incentives are both less than 0.01; therefore, it can be said that there is a significant positive relationship to the likelihood of purchasing health coverage for parents. Therefore, the hypotheses are accepted.

Table 4a. ANOVA_b of Equation 1.

MODEL		SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.
1	Regression	57.454	2	28.727	209.572	.000 ^b
	Residual	46.880	342	.137		
	Total	104.334	344			

- a. Dependent Variable: Attitude towards Tax Exemption for Purchasing Health Coverage for Parents.
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Intention to Support Tax Incentive in Purchasing Health Insurance for Parents, Likelihood to Purchase Health Coverage for Parents.

The simple regression model $F=209.572$ means that there is a significance between attitude towards tax exemption for purchasing health coverage for parents and likelihood to purchase health coverage for parents and the intention to support tax incentive in purchasing health insurance for parents with p-value (0.000) < 0.01.

Table 4b. ANOVA_b of Equation 2.

MODEL		SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.
2	Regression	81.748	2	40.874	114.174	.000 ^b
	Residual	122.434	342	.358		
	Total	204.182	344			

- a. Dependent Variable: Intention to Support Tax Incentives in Purchasing Health Insurance for Parents.
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Likelihood to Purchase Health Coverage for Parents, Attitude towards Tax Exemption for Purchasing Health Coverage for Parents.

The simple regression model $F=114.174$ shows that there is a significance between the intention to support tax incentives in purchasing health insurance for parents and attitude towards tax exemption for purchasing health coverage for parents and likelihood to purchase health coverage for parents with p-value (0.000) < 0.01.

CONCLUSION

Our study respondents were mainly aged 21 to 30, and a little over half were female. Besides that, most respondents were of Malay race, and most were married with no children. The majority did not wish to state their occupation and had an average monthly income of RM3,000 to RM3,999. Most of our respondents did not have any previous health problems, and most were involved with caring for their parents. The majority of the respondents also agreed that their parents were suffering from chronic diseases. Most respondents say their parents' average monthly medical expenses were RM500 and below. This overall profile was consistent with a study by (Alavi et al., 2011), where most adult children cared for parents with chronic diseases. As diabetes and hypertension become Malaysia's primary threats to healthy living, the most vulnerable group remains the elderly.

Our study findings show that working adults are highly likely to purchase insurance for their respective parents. This is because the elderly population in Malaysia are vulnerable to chronic disease and healthcare utilisations, which have a high cost. This study shows that working adults have a positive attitude and perception towards a tax exemption for purchasing parent's insurance covering pre-existing illness. Based on the results obtained from regression analysis on SPSS, the p-value was 0.00 for the likelihood of purchasing health coverage for parents, which is less than the alpha level of 0.01. Therefore, it can be said that there is a positive attitude towards tax exemption for purchasing parents' health insurance.

Most respondents agreed that tax rebate incentives will motivate them to purchase insurance for their parents. This significant finding highlighted the role of disposable income in health insurance purchases. About 50% of families with a self-employed person are more likely to purchase health insurance coverage, compared to 66% of families with a person employed in a government position or corporate position were more likely to be covered (Abdel-Ghany & Wang, 2001).

The findings of this study have shown that working adults have significant intentions to support tax exemption for parents' health coverage purchases. Previous studies generally suggest that taxpayers will be more likely to comply when that country's tax system is perceived to be fair. In addition to perceptions of tax fairness, other factors have also been recognised as important determinants of tax compliance behaviour, including the taxpayer's knowledge of the country's tax system, the complexity of the tax system and the attitude of individuals towards compliance. Such incentives will generate excess demand for health insurance, resulting in excess demand for health services. If a tax exemption is integrated into purchasing health coverage for parents, it will benefit many and lessen the medical expenses that consumers need to bear. Tax exemptions and incentives will lead to purchasing more substantial health insurance.

In this research, we have studied Malaysian working adults' perception of tax exemption for purchasing insurance for parents with pre-existing illnesses. The outcome of this research shows that working adults in Malaysia are likely to purchase insurance for their respective parents, have a more positive attitude and perception towards a tax exemption for purchasing parent's insurance covering pre-existing illness and have an intention to working adults to support on tax exemptions for parent's health coverage purchase. However, there are limitations to this study, and there is a potential for future works to address these limitations, which may serve as suggestions or a reference for others.

It cannot be used to analyse behavioural patterns. It is hard to determine behavioural patterns since the timing of the snapshot is not guaranteed to be representative of the study population as a whole. In addition, cross-sectional studies are also susceptible to bias; in this case, they could be responder bias and recall bias, which could also impact the result of this study.

The study population does not represent the entire working adult population in Malaysia. Most of the respondents were from the Klang Valley due to time and financial constraints. More extensive research should be conducted, including samples from all thirteen states and three federal territories, to gain more impactful findings.

Qualitative research should be done as is primarily exploratory research. It is used to gain an understanding of underlying reasons, opinions and motivations concerning the tax exemption for health insurance. Doing quantitative research helps us provide insights into the problem. In addition, this form of research could also help researchers to develop ideas or hypotheses for potential quantitative research. Qualitative research can also be used to uncover trends in thoughts and opinions and dive deeper into the problem. This is an essential tool to help us to generate ideas on ways to improve the policy better. Doing focus groups, group discussions, individual interviews, and participation/observations could be the key to helping us better understand this topic.

An economic study should be conducted to develop a model that would predict a reduction in public hospital congestion and operational costs if this tax exemption is approved. That would give further credibility and justification to approve tax exemption for working adults who buy health insurance for their parents, who are elderly citizens.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict-of-interest present.

REFERENCES

- Abdel-Ghany, M., & Wang, M. Q. (2001). Factors Associated with Different Degrees of Health Insurance Coverage. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 29(3), 252–264. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077727X01293003>
- Ackah, C., & Owusu, A. (2012). *Assessing the Knowledge of and Attitude towards Insurance in Ghana*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Assessing-the-Knowledge-of-and-Attitude-towards-in-Ackah-Owusu/6210cbdcbe9039e4cdc7326a609652a687043d0d>

- Alavi, K., Md. Sail, R., Mohamad, M. S., Omar, M., Subhi, N., Chong, S. T., Sarnon @ Kusenin, N., Ibrahim, F., & Mohamad, L. @ Z. (2011). Exploring the meaning of ageing and quality of life for the sub-urban older people. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*, 19(S), Article S.
- Blodgett, J. G., Hill, D. J., & Tax, S. S. (1997). The effects of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice on postcomplaint behavior. *Journal of Retailing*, 73(2), 185–210. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(97\)90003-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(97)90003-8)
- Brown, S. W., & Swartz, T. A. (1989). A gap analysis of professional service quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 53(2), 92–98. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1251416>
- Burnett, J. J., & Palmer, B. A. (1984). Examining Life Insurance Ownership through Demographic and Psychographic Characteristics. *The Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 51(3), 453. <https://doi.org/10.2307/252479>
- Cai, J., de Janvry, A., & Sadoulet, E. (2015). Social Networks and the Decision to Insure. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 7, 81–108. <https://doi.org/10.1257/app.20130442>
- Chen, Y., & Jin, G. Z. (2012). Does health insurance coverage lead to better health and educational outcomes? Evidence from rural China. *Journal of Health Economics*, 31(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhealeco.2011.11.001>
- Duodu, F., & Amankwah, T. (2012). *An Analysis and Assessment of Customer Satisfaction with Service Quality in Insurance Industry in Ghana*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/An-Analysis-and-Assessment-of-Customer-Satisfaction-Duodu-Amankwah/f2ea813b4e5c3ec8cc534261586bb23deff14d8f>
- Glied, S., & Jackson, A. (2017). The Future of the Affordable Care Act and Insurance Coverage. *American Journal of Public Health*, 107(4), 538–540. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2017.303665>
- Institute for Public Health—NHMS*. (2019). <https://iku.moh.gov.my/nhms-2019>
- Kumar, K., & Namavaram, R. (2016). A Study on Factors Influencing the Consumers in Selection of Cab Services. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 4, 557–561.
- Loke, Y., & Goh, Y. (2013). Purchase Decision of Life Insurance Policies among Malaysians. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 415–420. <https://doi.org/10.7763/IJSSH.2012.V2.137>

- Mohd Sidik, S., Mohd Zulkefli, N. A., & Mustaqim, A. (2003). Prevalence of depression with chronic illness among the elderly in a rural community in Malaysia. *Asia Pacific Family Medicine*, 2(4), 196–199. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1444-1683.2003.00100.x>
- Montgomery, R. J., Gonyea, J. G., & Hooyman, N. R. (1985). Caregiving and the experience of subjective and objective burden. *Family Relations: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Applied Family Studies*, 34(1), 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.2307/583753>
- Nair, S. S., & Devi, S. S. (2015). An autoethnographic vignette: The case of tax relief and sibling caregivers in Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 8, 179–206.
- Pliska, S. R., & Ye, J. (2007). Optimal life insurance purchase and consumption/investment under uncertain lifetime. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 31(5), 1307–1319.
- Sun, Y., Liu, N., & Zhao, M. (2019). Factors and mechanisms affecting green consumption in China: A multilevel analysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 209, 481–493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.10.241>
- Ulbinaitė, A., Kucinskiene, M., & Le Moullec, Y. (2013). Determinants of Insurance Purchase Decision Making in Lithuania. *Inzinerine Ekonomika-Engineering Economics*, 24, 144–159. <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.2.24.2.3439>
- van Doorslaer, E., Masseria, C., Koolman, X., & OECD Health Equity Research Group. (2006). Inequalities in access to medical care by income in developed countries. *CMAJ: Canadian Medical Association Journal = Journal de l'Association Medicale Canadienne*, 174(2), 177–183. <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.050584>
- World Health Organization. (2013). *Mental health of older adults*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-of-older-adults>
- World health report: 2002. (n.d.). Retrieved August 4, 2023, from <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9241562072>